

Neuroevolution of Spiking Neural Networks

by

Kade M. Heckel

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Department of Informatics

Head of Department: Dr. Ian Mackie
Supervisor: Dr. Thomas Nowotny

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Abstract

While incredible achievements have been attained using 2nd generation artificial neural networks (ANN) in the past few years, the computational and financial resources required to train and deploy models at scale pose a significant challenge. While endeavors like knowledge distillation, weight pruning, and quantization attempt to reduce computational demand in ANN architectures, they often lead to significant quality loss for smaller models in resource-constrained setups; in contrast, the emerging field of neuromorphic computing addresses these issues by adapting hardware and network structures using energy-efficient principles inspired by biology. Using the brain as a blueprint, neuromorphic systems depart from ANN architectures by limiting neurons to only communicate via binary spikes; such a construction allows for the elimination of multiplication of floating point values and opens the door for asynchronous and event-triggered computation, vastly reducing the complexity and power demands of hardware. These benefits are not reaped for free however as the all-or-nothing firing in spiking neural networks (SNN) introduces new challenges in the training process as their discontinuous dynamics yield an ill-defined gradient when performing optimization. Hailed as the 3rd generation of neural computation, recent SNN optimization has been facilitated by surrogate gradient methods which perform Back Propagation Through Time (BPTT) with a smoothed approximation of the spiking activation function's gradient. However, while surrogate gradients address the concern that exact gradient methods are ignorant of spike generation or deletion, they still face the issue of dead neurons which once completely silent cannot trigger weight updates. Neuroevolution, a gradient-free optimization approach that had fallen out of favor until recent years due computational constraints, provides a resolution to these challenges by circumventing the non-differentiability of spiking activation functions. This thesis brings two distinct contributions: firstly, the introduction of a new framework called Spyx, which enhances SNN training speed by an order of magnitude, and secondly, an exploration of modern neuroevolution's effectiveness for SNNs, demonstrating competitive performance with gradient-based methods across multiple benchmark datasets.

Statement of Original Authorship

"I hereby certify that the submitted work is my own work, was completed while registered as a candidate for the degree stated on the Title Page, and I have not obtained a degree elsewhere on the basis of the research presented in this submitted work"

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Dedication

To Mark; Love ya' Pops.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

While just the training of even a 110M parameter BERT-base model in 2019 was estimated to have a carbon footprint on par with a commercial flight from New York to San Francisco, the greater environmental and financial cost of deep learning lies in the large scale deployment of models for inference where hundreds or thousands of copies of the model are instantiated across digital infrastructure for constant access(97). More recently, large language models such as GPT-3 which has 175 billion parameters require distributed execution across a small cluster of data-center GPUs, making their scalability to high-volume applications such as internet search a troubling issue in terms of environmental and financial cost.

Additionally, deploying machine learning capabilities in remote environments is a major challenge, as devices may be disconnected from both a constant power supply and/or communications, in addition to having to operate on less-capable hardware. These constraints are common in fields such as robotics, IoT devices, and remote sensing. In each of these domains, energy is constrained, radio frequency bandwidth is limited, and latency may be an issue. In such settings, deploying massive ANN models at the edge is impractical, as hardware with sufficient computational capacity is too resource intensive and hosting the model remotely poses reliability issues in the case of network degradation or failure. While efforts such as knowledge distillation, weight pruning, and quantization have been employed to mitigate the computational demands of ANN architectures, these techniques can result in quality degradation for smaller models operating within resource-constrained environments(60).

In contrast to these approaches, the emerging field of neuromorphic computing offers a novel perspective on addressing these challenges by reimagining hardware and network structures based on energy-efficient principles inspired by biological systems. This departure from traditional ANN models involves constraining neurons to communicate solely through binary spikes, eliminating the need for complex floating point multiplications. Consequently, this design enables asynchronous and event-triggered computation, leading to significantly reduced complexity and power requirements in hardware systems. Examples of neuromorphic hardware include Intel's Loihi or the BrainDrop system from Stanford, (17; 71) while example applications include onboard neuromorphic processors are used for robotic control investigated by the Brains on Board Project and or for potential use as on-orbit signal detection models in satellites (16; 18).

Nonetheless, these advantages do not come without their own set of challenges. Spiking neural networks (SNNs), representing the third generation of neural computation, introduce a new dimension to the training process due to their all-or-nothing firing dynamics. This leads to issues with

optimization, as the discontinuous nature of SNN dynamics produces gradients that are ill-defined; specifically, the spiking behavior is brought about through the use of the Heaviside function the derivative of which is equal to zero everywhere except zero where it is infinite. Additionally, the deep learning revolution has been powered by drastic improvements in parallel processing which is not beneficial for SNNs which can be interpreted as a special recurrent neural network (RNN) with binary activations(73).

Given the wealth of knowledge wrought by the deep learning revolution for training non-recurrent ANNs, a common approach is to either convert an ANN to a spiking equivalent or jointly train an ANN and SNN leveraging the well defined gradients of the former. While conversion and hybrid methods offer the promise to quickly generate spiking models with competitive performance, early techniques came with the caveat that the converted models had significant inference latency and high firing rates which are inefficient; recent work has investigated remedies to these issues and remains important for translating the state-of-the-art models powering today's economy to more efficient hardware.

To avoid latency issues and achieve better sparsity, the other main effort in SNN optimization has focused on their direct training through surrogate gradient methods, which employ Backpropagation Through Time (BPTT) with a smoothed approximation of the spiking activation when calculating gradients. Unlike exact gradient methods such as EventProp(105) that have no awareness of spike creation or deletion(75), the smoothing of surrogate gradient methods allow for "dead" neurons which have ceased firing altogether to still transmit gradient information and possibly be revived. Even armed with a gradient, the next issue that arises is that SNNs face the same challenges as RNNs where over long time horizons the gradient can either vanish or explode. This phenomena can be partially mitigated by using local learning rules but the issue remains that the surrogate gradient calculated may not be aligned with the direction of greatest improvement (26; 73).

A compelling alternative solution emerges through the technique of neuroevolution, an approach to optimization that operates without gradients. Sidestepping the challenges posed by non-differentiable spiking activation functions, neuroevolution allows weight updates to occur without requiring spikes and effectively addresses the problem of inactive neurons within SNNs. Additionally, SNNs designed for embedded systems typically have low parameter counts which facilitates their massively parallel evaluation on modern AI accelerators. Up to this point, however, spiking neuroevolution research has primarily utilized Neuroevolution of Augmenting Topologies (NEAT) to explore the coevolution of network weights and structure for small scale models. Recent advancements in computer hardware and new tools have made it possible to use evolution strategies to optimize neural network parameters on a single device. This renders techniques that were once only possible with large compute clusters accessible and practical.(57)

This thesis introduces Spyx, a new framework for training SNNs within the JAX ecosystem. JAX is a Python library for high-performance array computing that provides auto-differentiation and code vectorization capabilities for machine learning and scientific computing applications through just-in-time (JIT) compilation to efficient kernels for execution on GPUs and TPUs. (2) By leveraging the power of JAX, Spyx provides a flexible, modular, and extensible set of tools for training SNNs in minimal time through both surrogate gradient and neuroevolutionary approaches. The following chapters will provide background on what makes SNNs distinct and how they are trained before showcasing aspects of Spyx and evaluating it on several neuromorphic datasets.

Chapter 2

An Overview of Spiking Neural Networks

2.1 Neuron Models

2.1.1 The Perceptron (1st Generation)

Initial work on neuron-inspired machine learning models began in the 1940's with the investigation of the squid giant axon by McCulloch and Pitts. Seeking to emulate the dynamics of biological neurons, they proposed a mathematical model where a weighted sum of input currents is calculated and a binary spike is emitted if the value exceeds a threshold, mimicking the emission of an action potential by a biological neuron if its dendrites are sufficiently stimulated(66). This firing model described below is based on the Heaviside function and while it was discarded in favor of differentiable functions during the deep learning revolution, it has come back into the fold in spiking neural network research which will be discussed shortly. In this model, if the dot product of the inputs \vec{x} and weights \vec{w} plus a biasing term b exceed 0, a spike is generated as shown in the following equation:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \vec{w} \cdot \vec{x} + b > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

With this simple hard-threshold neuron model, data can be perfectly classified so long as it is linearly separable; in other words, there exists a hyperplane that bisects the data. The supervised learning rule for this model was developed by Rosenblatt in the 1960's while working for the US Office of Naval Research(87). While the initial system was optimized via a rudimentary sign-based learning rule, concurrent work by Widrow and Hoff pioneered the use of the mean squared error between the target values and the predictions as the loss function to minimize using gradient descent techniques(102). However, computational limitations of the time period prevented the investigation of deeper networks of perceptron/neuron models, and neural networks suffered through an "AI Winter" after Minsky and Papert demonstrated that a single layer perceptron is incapable of learning the XOR function due to it not being linearly separable.(69)

2.1.2 Artificial Neural Networks (2nd Generation)

The second generation of artificial neural networks came into prominence with the deep learning revolution when computer hardware had advanced significantly. While work in the 1990's saw improvements with recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and their application to long sequences with the LSTM(44), It was the utilization GPUs originally intended for speeding up the linear algebra inten-

sive graphics computations to instead perform neural network computations with the landmark paper introducing AlexNet for computer vision(56). Over the years, new continuous valued activation functions and loss objectives were introduced and the variety of network architectures exploded thanks to automatic differentiation software such as TensorFlow(1), PyTorch(80), and JAX(2), allowing for easy calculation of gradients for networks. Notable milestones in the deep learning revolution include the introduction of convolutional neural networks, which remain a pillar of modern computer-vision models, and the development of the transformer architecture in 2017 (100) which kicked off a wave of advances in natural language processing culminating in the advent of large language models, vision transformers, and various multi-modal foundation models.

2.1.3 Spiking Neural Networks (3rd Generation)

The Spiking Neural Networks investigated in this work are based on Leaky Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) neuron models as well as more complex versions that possess adaptive membrane thresholds in order to exhibit more diverse dynamics and are inspired by the `snnTorch` library(26). SNNs can be seen as a reimagining of RNN models with specific properties that facilitate their use in resource constrained settings and specialized hardware. Succinctly put, SNN architectures like their RNN relatives have an internal state that evolves in time based on previous values, with the notable exception being the use of binary activation functions(73).

A basic 3rd generation neuron model is one that operates passively without a non-linearity and does not spike at all; the following equation details a continuous time Leaky-Integrate (LI) neuron:

$$\tau \frac{dV(t)}{dt} = -V(t) + I_{in}(t)R$$

Where $V(t)$ is the membrane potential, τ is the time constant reflecting the decay rate of the membrane potential, and $I_{in}(t)$ is the injected current to the neuron moderated by a resistance R . This differential has an exponential closed form solution as follows, where V_0 is the initial membrane potential:

$$V(t) = I_{in}(t)R + [V_0 - I_{in}(t)R]e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}$$

This closed form solution can be converted into a discrete recurrence relation through the use of a single-step Euler method, making it possible to implement in a manner similar to recurrent neural networks.

$$V[t] = \beta V[t - 1] + (1 - \beta)RI_{in}[t]$$

This work follows the approach in utilized in the `SNN_Torch` library(26), where the input current $I_{in}[t]$ is treated as the input data $X[t]$ which is weighted with a learned weight matrix \mathbf{W} which accounts for the factors of $(1 - \beta)$ and R . Additionally, to make the neuron model active, a spiking component is added to the dynamics equation, where $S_{out}[t]$ is the Heaviside step function and θ is the firing threshold. With this addition, the Leaky-Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) model is derived, which is shown below for a flat layer although it applies to higher order tensors as well in the case of convolutional layers:

$$\vec{S}_i[t] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \vec{V}_i[t] > \theta \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\vec{V}[t] = \beta\vec{V}[t - 1] + \mathbf{W}\vec{X}[t] - \vec{S}[t]\theta$$

The LIF neuron model with the application of Euler’s method can be cast as a recurrent neural network with time-dependent binary activations, where the membrane voltage $V[t]$ is the network’s recurrent state and β acts as an implicit recurrent connection that decays the state vector over time to remember more recent inputs. Simpler Integrate-and-Fire models which eliminate β are also common in neuromorphic computing research due to their simplicity for implementing in low power hardware at the expense of the model’s temporal expressiveness; one such architecture to do this was IBM’s TrueNorth(20). While treating the inverse time constant β as a learned parameter has been shown to improve model performance, implementing them in hardware may prove challenging; an alternative method to simplify the implementation of LIF neurons in digital hardware is to constrain $\beta = 0.5$ such that it can be implemented using arithmetic shift operations(70). More complex neuron models that incorporate explicit and weighted recurrent connections as well as adaptive firing thresholds are also possible and implemented in Spyx.

2.2 Computing with Spikes

Guided by evolutionary pressures to maximize utility and minimize energy consumption, biological neural networks adopt several strategies to achieve incredible results. At the smallest scales of life, unicellular organisms can rely purely on chemical receptors on their cell membranes and passive diffusion to efficiently assimilate analog information about the environment and perform tasks such as chemotaxis. While effective at extremely short ranges and highly energy efficient, passive diffusion possesses the dynamics of a random walk with a signalling strength that decays quadratically with distance making it untenable as the primary signalling method in larger multi-cellular organisms. The innovation to overcome these challenges lies in neural circuitry’s conversion of chemical signals into binary electrical impulses which can reliably and quickly travel long distances; these spikes come at the cost of energy however, and as such sparsity becomes a necessity. For a comprehensive treatment of the principles of neural design, see the book *Principles of Neural Design* by Sterling and Laughlin(96).

The paradigm of enforcing binary inter-neuron communication with local analog processing would drastically simplify the implementation of neural network models. For example, Google’s Tensor Processing Units (TPUs) are application-specific processors designed specifically for training and deploying second generation deep neural networks and is configured as a systolic array of multiply-add units that operate on 16 bit floating point representations(49). In contrast, an SNN implemented on neuromorphic hardware would only need to communicate a single bit between accumulator units thereby eliminating the need for floating point multiplication and shrinking the hardware footprint substantially.

The remaining question is how to go about transforming information such as audio or video into spikes as well as how to train an SNN to compute in spikes. Again drawing inspiration from biology and neuroscience, three input and output spike coding schemes emerge: rate, temporal, and delta modulation. While SNNs usually select a single scheme but not necessarily matching schemes for encoding inputs and outputs, biological neural networks such as the human brain likely operate using a mixture of all three methods(26).

2.2.1 Firing Rate Coding

Rate coding for SNNs presumes that information is encoded by the number of spikes emitted by a neuron, with more spikes translating to stronger signal intensity. While there is evidence for rate based coding in at least some portions of the brain, its energy inefficient nature does not make it plausible that the entire brain operates in such a mode. Rate based encoding for SNNs offer a form of convenience as they enable rather straightforward conversion of second generation ANN models to spiking equivalents by interpreting ReLU activations in an ANN as the firing rate for an IF neuron in a SNN. Similarly, static data can be easily converted by normalizing the values to between zero and one and using them as probabilities for sampling Bernoulli random values. While the increased spiking of rate coding offers the advantages in terms of resilience and easier learning via surrogate gradient descent, it comes at the cost of speed and power efficiency. Rate based SNNs require a sufficient timescale in order to distinguish between inputs and also provide appropriately differentiated predictions; too short of a time frame prevents neurons from spiking enough times unless a population code of multiple neurons per class is used at the expense of additional spikes. Rate-based SNNs can be easily trained using crossentropy or mean-square error (MSE) losses on the sum of either the output spikes or the final layer's membrane potential. (26)

2.2.2 Spike Timing

An alternative and more sparse method for interpreting SNN activity is through spike timing, where the first output neuron to spike is determined to be the network decision. By using the timing of spikes to encode decisions and data, SNNs and their inputs can express information in a more compact fashion requiring less time steps and spikes than rate based approaches; this comes with the trade-off that relying on the timing of spikes to express predictions can be more sensitive to noise as well as more susceptible to the dead neuron problem since less spikes are present for triggering weight updates during backpropagation. While at first it remains unclear how a biological neural network would use temporal coding when there is no distinct beginning or end of sensory information, when combined with delta modulation it becomes understandable how temporal decisions are made based on changes in sensory information. For timing-coded SNN models, the loss functions are more difficult to construct as a crossentropy based objective needs to convert earlier spike times into larger values while Mean-Squared-Error (MSE) based losses need to specify either exact or relative spike times; these approaches are more difficult to implement and train due to the reduced spike activity, making surrogate gradient descent more challenging. (26)

2.2.3 Delta Modulation

On a bio-physical basis, the repeated encoding and transmission of sensory would be redundant and therefore wasteful of energy. Instead, there would be tremendous evolutionary incentive for neurons to only transmit changes in information. (96) Similarly, the theory of predictive processing in neuroscience posits that the brain acts as a generative model of the world and then seeks to explain away differences between the internal model and the sensory input received; since only changes in inputs are being processed, redundant spiking is eliminated thereby improving energy efficiency. Neuromorphic computing research to date has primarily explored delta modulation as only a method for encoding input data for example with dynamic vision sensors(26) however it is also possible for use in a predictive coding approach where input reconstruction is the training objective. (5; 79)

2.3 SNN Architectures

2.3.1 Convolutional SNNs (CSNNs)

Convolutions have remained a powerful structure for neural network architectures, especially for those dealing with visual information. Unsurprisingly, using convolutions to introduce the same inductive prior on SNNs results in better performance, as shown when CSNNs achieve 96.7% accuracy on the DVS-Gesture dataset.(89) Further work has sought to convert full ResNet architectures into spiking equivalents, with the Spike-Element Wise ResNet being a prominent milestone in deep spiking neural network research, attaining 97.9% on DVS-Gesture and almost 70% on Imagenet. (28)

2.3.2 Recurrent SNNs (RSNNs)

Recent research has shown that incorporating explicit recurrence in SNN architectures enables the model to learn richer temporal representations than architectures that only rely on implicit recurrence modeled through decay of the membrane voltage. One reason for why explicit connections can be advantageous is that they can inhibit or excite other neurons in the same layer to ease the learning of distinct activity patterns; at the same time, care must be taken such that the recurrent connections do not create instability in the network by driving a neuron to continuous firing. RSNNs have become a common architecture in the literature, with a recent example being found in a recent work where an RSNN network with adaptive LIF neurons was able to achieve competitive performance on the SHD dataset(8). Other work on RSNNs involves the introduction of gating mechanisms from RNNs such as spiking LSTMs, for example LSTM-LIF which is a "two-compartment" model that excels at modeling longer term dependencies when compared to standard LIF models(112).

2.3.3 Transformer Inspired Architectures

Given the explosion in public attention toward the field of artificial intelligence following the release of OpenAI's ChatGPT and the domination of transformer-based ANN models in natural language processing and computer vision, it is unsurprising that attempts to create spiking versions of the encoder-decoder and decoder only SNNs have been investigated. Given the massive demand for applying generative AI and language models to all aspects of business, it would be tremendously advantageous both economically and environmentally if these multi-billion parameter models could be run on much more efficient neuromorphic hardware rather than clusters of GPUs. Of these spiking attention models, the aptly named SpikeGPT weighs in at an impressive 216 million parameter count, making it the largest SNN to date. Its architecture is an extrapolation of RWKV, an efficient and powerful RNN designed to achieve competitive performance to transformer models while having lower parameter counts. An extremely appealing aspect of the RWKV architecture is the fact that it can be trained using convolutions and can perform inference as an RNN, an attribute that is attractive for the paradigm of training on high-performance GPUs and deploying on neuromorphic hardware(9; 116). This recurrent formulation of attention is in contrast with other transformer-inspired SNN architectures such as Spikeformer, Spikformer, and Spikingformer which both implement QKV attention mechanisms and have cubic computational complexity due to attention being applied recurrently across a sequence(59; 114; 115).

2.4 Connections to Other Lines of Neural Network Research

2.4.1 Binarized and Quantized Neural Networks

The characteristics and objectives of quantized and binarized ANNs overlap with those of SNNs, with all three designs targeting the reduction of model computational cost through sparsity and reduced precision. SNNs and binarized ANNs (BiNNs) both possess specialized binary activation functions, with the latter also constraining its weights to be ± 1 ; while normally SNNs have floating point weights, there have also been binarized variations(24; 25; 48).

Binarized neural networks prompted the concept of straight-through estimation for gradients in order to circumvent the non-differentiable aspects of the network. The notion of copying gradients through non-differentiable operations is also employed in quantization-aware training for lower precision floating point ANN architectures, where at each step the weights are quantized before performing the forward pass(46) and has shown to be outperform quantization after the fact. Quantization-aware training also shares many aspects with mixed precision training where some aspects of the model are computed at different numerical precision levels(68). In a way, surrogate gradient methods for SNNs can be viewed as a version of quantization-aware training on the activation function, where a differentiable function such as a sigmoid is replaced with the Heaviside during the forward pass.

2.4.2 Phasor Neural Networks (PNNs)

A recent line of work that has connections to SNNs deals with phasor neural networks (PNNs). Somewhat similar to conversion methods, the neuron activations in a PNN represent the angle of a unitary complex number known as a phasor. In such an architecture, each layer computes a linear combination of the previous layer's values to form a superposition and computes a new phase angle. The intriguing property of PNNs is that they can be trained atemporally like an ANN and then executed over a temporal dimension as a SNN. This offers the exciting prospect of efficient training on GPUs before deployment on neuromorphic hardware without having the same disadvantages of conventional conversion methods that result in large inference latency. It is important to note that phasor networks utilize temporal rather than rate coding, opening the door to greater power efficiency. For phasor networks, inputs are mapped to a unitary phasor whose angle is a function of the input value and outputs are the phases of the last layer. The advantage of Spiking PNNs is that they convert the task of training spike times in SNNs into training the phase of the network's output using autodifferentiation on complex vectors, allowing for non-recurrent training of a model which can then be converted to an SNN for deployment and inference(12). Investigations thus far demonstrate 1% test error on the MNIST dataset and 30% error on CIFAR, offering promise for future research using more complex architectures suited for the image processing domain(12; 77). Other work with phasor networks include their use in threshold-phasor associative memories, which has connections to Hopfield networks and could play a role in active memory components of SNN architectures deployed on neuromorphic hardware(29).

2.4.3 Closed-Form Continuous Time Networks

Connections between SNNs and the field of Neural Differential Equations (NDEs) also exist; indeed, the recurrent formulation of neuron models is derived using an Euler approximation of the dynamics, turning a continuous valued dynamical system into a recurrence relation. As opposed to discretizing

and then computing the network's outputs, the research area of neural differential applies a host of numerical solvers such as Runge-Kutta methods to compute the values thus allowing adaptive computation steps to keep numerical errors below a target threshold. NDEs have shown to be competitive with other state-of-the-art RNN models such as those built on Long-Short Term Memory cells and are valuable in scenarios where data might be missing. There are a few classes of NDEs that model ordinary, controlled, and stochastic differential equations; each of these models add different modeling capabilities that are suited for different scenarios. Neural ODEs can be viewed as a continuous-depth feed-forward neural network. Neural Controlled Differential Equations, however, permit for the input to also vary with time; this allows for RNN-like behavior while not being constrained to sample at regular time intervals which has tremendous benefit in real-world applications where data may not be sampled uniformly in time such as in healthcare(51).

Work on translating biological neuron dynamics into the realm of Neural Differential Equations has led to the development of Liquid-Time Constant Networks, which adopt a Leaky-Integrate neuron model with sigmoidal activations instead of binary spikes; these systems are then solved using a numerical solver like other NDEs while exhibiting greater stability. More recently, the same authors derived a closed form solution that removes the need to utilize a numerical solver, creating the Closed-form Continuous-time network model that is substantially faster in both training and inference and have been tested for use in applications such as autonomous vehicles and the control of aerial drones(37; 39).

While there are parallels between SNNs and the line of work on NDEs, the latter stays away from the sparse spiking behavior conducive for deployment on neuromorphic hardware; despite this, the idea for trying to remove dependence on costly temporal evaluation is good inspiration for work in SNNs. Finally and most recently an adaptation of LTC networks drawing on insights from structured state space models was able to set new state-of-the-art performances on several long range benchmark tasks, lying at the intersection of work on NDEs and State Space Machine models which will be discussed next(38).

2.4.4 State Space Machines

Connections between State Space Machines (SSMs) and SNNs exist through the decomposition of neuron models into two separate components. By working with only Leaky-Integrate neurons the model can be treated as a linear-time invariant (LTI) system that can be efficiently computed using convolutions and the Fourier transform. The spiking component of the system can then be reintroduced as a stochastic operation dependent on the membrane voltage; this approach enables for the LI neuron model to be trained orders of magnitude faster on GPUs (106).

This approach has several exciting prospects as several state-spaced machine learning models have recently been found to perform incredibly well on long range dependency benchmarks in language modeling and operate using an LTI system. If the same stochastic spiking method could be applied to these SSM models, they could be adapted for use on neuromorphic hardware and achieve competitive performance with transformer architecture models at substantially lower power draw. Given the recent work on using the RNN-based RWKV architecture to create a spiking language model, the investigation of spiking SSM models appears to be a topic ripe to be explored. Like RWKV, these SSM models also possess the ability to be trained in a convolutional manner and then perform inference using recurrently, making them an excellent target for future research on advanced neuromorphic computing models (32; 94).

Chapter 3

Training Spiking Neural Networks

3.1 Shadow Training: Conversion, Hybridization, and Distillation

Since the training of ANNs is well handled through gradient descent, several lines of work have explored either converting ANNs to SNNs directly or training both simultaneously as part of hybrid architecture and distillation schemes to overcome the discontinuity of a spiking network's dynamics. Grouped together, these methods can be termed shadow training as the SNN model is learned indirectly through the optimization of an ANN(26).

An early work seeking to train models for use on IBM's TrueNorth chip trained small recurrent ANN using backpropagation through time; the model was then translated onto hardware by using an integrate-and-fire neuron model for which the firing rate would mimic the RNN's ReLU activation functions. (20) More recent conversion research such as the method in (92) achieved performance comparable to the ANN models they were converted from, however this came at the cost of the SNNs taking thousands time steps for inference. In such approaches, ReLU neurons are converted to LIF spiking models by re-scaling the weights from the ANN such that when used in an SNN the LIF neuron's firing rate approximates the ReLU output; besides the latency issue of requiring a large number of iterations, this method doesn't apply for inherently temporal data such as events recorded by a neuromorphic camera and also leads to extremely high firing rates which are counterproductive for deployment on efficient hardware. Further research into optimizing ANN2SNN conversion has revolved around trying to convert large pretrained networks such as VGG, ResNets, or YOLO architectures to spiking models while keeping the required simulation time down. (19)

Another significant gap in rate-based conversion of ANNs to SNNs besides latency and a lack of sparsity is that they can only work with non-negative activation values and therefore excluding models such as EfficientNet which contain SiLU functions. An alternative that could address all of these issues would be to utilize temporal coding, allowing for an ANN to be emulated with as few as two spikes on average. (98)

Other work has sought to jointly train both an ANN and SNN, using the former as either a differentiable surrogate or a teacher model to distill information into the latter. One work (33) trained both networks simultaneously with a shared set of factorized weights using a multi-component loss function combining cross-entropy prediction loss with a KL-Divergence loss between the ANN and SNN outputs and an L2 loss between the hidden layer representations, achieving competitive results on computer vision benchmarks. The partial weight sharing through using the singular value decompo-

sition is an interesting approach as it allows for the SNN to learn an effective re-scaling of the ANN weights while only requiring a small number of time-steps.

Another distillation approach addressed the issue of excessive latency found in (92) by using layer-wise distillation with attention mechanisms, yielding competitive performance with ANNs on several benchmark vision datasets while requiring 20 times fewer time-steps compared to other methods for ANN-to-SNN conversion. (45) This work used a method of initializing the student SNN model with the parameters of a converted ANN, a technique previously used in a different hybrid technique where an ANN was first converted before then being trained with surrogate gradient descent for a limited number of epochs. (86)

In summary, conversion methods remain a promising line of work for trying to adapt pretrained ANN architectures to more efficient hardware but are not as effective for developing new SNNs for tailored use-cases given the rise of surrogate gradient methods which have proven an effective way to train SNNs using backpropagation.

3.2 Gradient Propagation Learning Algorithms

3.2.1 Non-Backpropagation Based Gradient Methods.

The challenge with directly training SNNs is twofold; first, the binary spiking of neurons results in a derivative that is either zero or ill-defined and second, even armed with a gradient, the long time horizons over which SNNs operate introduce the same challenges faced by RNNs of exploding and vanishing gradients.

EventProp works around the discontinuities in the spiking dynamics of SNNs to calculate the true gradient by leveraging the adjoint method in combination with a second network that runs in reverse.(105) Further work has sought to increase the flexibility of EventProp by generalizing it to a wider range of loss functions and investigating loss shaping by applying an exponential decay factor to calculating the integral cross-entropy. (75) A major issue pertaining to optimizing with the exact gradient is that it does not know when small adjustments will result in spike generation or deletion and struggles with the divergence of the gradient magnitude as the membrane potential nears the firing threshold. Given these issues, methods that combine true and surrogate gradient information may pose an advantage and further work is needed to try and extend the method beyond LIF neuron models. (105) Additionally, given the connections to dynamical systems, there may be opportunity to leverage insights from research in Neural Differential Equations to improve true-gradient calculations of SNNs.

In contrast with EventProp, E-prop builds on Real-Time Recurrent Learning (RTRL) which is an alternative to Backpropagation Through Time (BPTT) for training recurrent neural networks. While traditional RTRL has higher computational demands than BPTT, by only leveraging locally available information E-prop is able to be more efficient while also becoming an online learning rule and has been used to implement on-chip learning on the SpiNNaker2 system. Another difference from EventProp is that E-prop uses a surrogate gradient of the spiking function rather than treating the discontinuities directly(4; 88). Finally, another RTRL variant is Forward Propagation Through Time (107) which instead calculates and minimizes a dynamic loss value during the forward pass of the SNN, posing the advantage of avoiding the need for computing a backward pass while still leveraging gradient-based learning.

Surrogate Function	Derivative
Straight Through Estimation(6)	1
Sigmoid	$\frac{e^{\theta-V}}{(e^{\theta-V}+1)^2}$
SuperSpike(110)	$\frac{1}{(1+k \theta-V)^2}$
Arctangent(26)	$\frac{1}{\pi(1+(\pi(\theta-V))^2)}$

Table 3.1: Examples of Surrogate Gradient Functions

3.2.2 Backpropagation Through Time with Surrogate Gradients

The most popular method for state-of-the-art training of SNNs is through the use of surrogate gradients. During the forward pass of the network the spiking neurons behave according to a Heaviside step function and for the backward pass the gradient is approximated using the derivative of smooth functions from the sigmoid family. More formally, using a sigmoid function shifted based on the neuron’s firing threshold θ yields the following:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{1 + e^{\theta-V}}$$

with the derivative of the surrogate function relative to the membrane potential being as follows(26):

$$\frac{\delta S}{\delta V} = \sigma' = \frac{e^{\theta-V}}{(e^{\theta-V} + 1)^2}$$

The motivation for using a differentiable relaxation of the activation function in the backwards pass of the network is to address the dead neuron problem: when a neuron’s weights reach the point where no spikes are emitted, it no longer receives weight updates and remains silent. While surrogate gradient methods do not completely address the dead neuron problem as they still require spikes for weight updates to occur, they do allow for dead neurons to propagate biased estimates of the gradient to earlier layers in the network. In order to mitigate dead neurons two approaches include lowering the firing threshold to cause firing or to apply regularization to the hidden layers to discourage firing rates that approach zero(26). Straight-through estimation, a method used in also non-differentiable binarized neural networks and in vector-quantized variational autoencoders for backpropagating through a discrete latent layer, can be viewed as the trivial case of surrogate gradients as the spiking function is assumed to be the identity function(6). A variety of alternative surrogate gradient functions have been explored with a number of different methods detailed in table 3.1; while some appear to perform better than others, research has found SNN learning to be quite robust to the choice of surrogate function(111) and tuning the learning rate can often mitigate the difference between one surrogate function and another.

3.3 Local Learning

An issue with the biological plausibility of backpropagation is the fact that updates for neurons in the initial layers of the network require precise information about a large number of forward-connecting synaptic weights downstream in the neural circuit; such a mechanism becomes especially unlikely when considering the scale and noisiness of the human brain, creating what is referred to as the weight transport problem(61). In neuroscience this issue is addressed by Predictive Processing,

a theory which posits that neurons adapt their firing behavior based on local inhibition from other neurons rather than making fine-grained adjustments based on long distance interactions. As such, a line of work has investigated the use of local learning rules which do not require the communication of weight values across a neural network model(14).

3.3.1 Reservoir Computing (RC)

One option to avoid the difficulty of backpropagating through spiking activations is to simply not train the spiking layers at all; indeed, this is the approach taken in Reservoir Computing, where the spiking/dynamical system portion of the network is left in its randomly initialized state, with only a linear decoding layer being optimized according to the linear least-squares regression. Since only the readout layer is trained, weight transport is avoided and RC can be viewed as the simplest case of local learning(31).

3.3.2 Random and Direct Feedback Alignment (RFA & DFA)

Somewhat shockingly, the most simple learning rule is Random Feedback Alignment (RFA), where the error signal/gradient from the network is multiplied by a random matrix rather than the transpose of the current layer's weight matrix. So long as the angle between the true gradient and the random matrix is acute, it will eventually converge to a similar result; while work remains in understanding the full nature of feedback alignment, research suggests that the learning process aligns the weights in accordance with the random matrix such that the gradient information then becomes useful(61). Despite RFA's simplicity it has even been utilized for training SNNs in hardware, demonstrating it's applicability(72). RFA was built upon with Direct Feedback alignment (DFA), where instead of using the gradient from the next layer to compute each layer's gradient is the objective function loss value multiplied against a random matrix, reducing the distance between the loss function and the weights in early layers(76). Feedback alignment methods and the DECOLLE method which followed them are built on a similar foundation as surrogate gradient methods in that they operate on a biased yet correlated estimate of the gradient which can be sufficient given proper circumstances(50).

3.3.3 Deep Continuous Local Learning (DECOLLE)

Deep Continuous Local Learning (DECOLLE) is similar to synthetic gradient approaches and can be viewed as an extension of feedback alignment methods. In DECOLLE, each layer is assigned a fixed and random readout layer, with the loss for the entire network comprising the sum of each of the readout layers. The gradient in DECOLLE is only defined locally as the product of the readout error times the surrogate gradient of the random readout times the parameters of the layer, all modulated by a learning rate (50).

A similar approach to DECOLLE was recently presented for ANNs except the network backbone is left untrained in favor of optimizing the linear decoders using a closed form solution and using and their predictions are combined as an ensemble. This Cascaded Forward algorithm can be viewed as a deep reservoir computing technique in essence(113).

In synthetic gradients, rather than backpropagating the actual gradient every training step, a model is learned to estimate the gradient feedback based on the output of the given layer. This allows the formation of "Decoupled Neural Interfaces", where layers of a neural network can be updated asynchronously and can be used to approximate the non-truncated gradient signal for training RNNs(47).

Another connection between the work of synthetic gradients and surrogate gradients can be found in research on differentiable approximation bridges, which sought to learn a model to approximate the gradient for any non-differentiable component of a computation graph, which when applied to a SNN would reduce to learning a surrogate gradient function (84).

3.4 Neuroevolution

3.4.1 Advantages of Neuroevolution

A possibility to train the weights of SNNs without computing gradients would be to use zero-order optimization methods, which predominantly entail evolutionary computation methods. In neuroevolution, a distribution of network parameters referred to as a population are evaluated according to a criterion (which does not necessarily need to be differentiable), with the results informing the exploration and exploitation of the parameter space. How the optimization progresses depends on the specific algorithm, with some maintaining an explicit population of parameters that are recombined using crossover and mutation whereas evolutionary strategies approaches only maintain and update statistics about the distribution of possible network parameters.

While the downside of zero order evolutionary methods is the requirement of many network evaluations per optimization step to estimate the gradient, these evaluations can be performed in parallel; helpfully, due to the target hardware being intentionally resource constrained, SNN architectures usually have a limited parameter count. As such, utilizing neuroevolution for optimizing SNNs is a feasible approach without require access to large amounts of resources for training. For example, a 500,000 parameter SNN with weights stored in 16-bit floating point representation only requires 1 MB of RAM to store; by extension, a population of 1,000 of these networks would only require 1 GB to store which is small relative to the 80 GB vRAM capacities of state-of-the-art GPUs.

An issue with surrogate gradient descent for SNNs is that the BPTT must be truncated in order to maintain a manageable memory complexity as otherwise the entire computation graph needs to be maintained which becomes prohibitively cost for long sequences and fine-grained temporal precision. Such truncation in fine-grained settings could pose an issue for training if the temporal dependencies in the spike trains are longer than the truncation window. In contrast, neuroevolution only needs the final output of the network for evaluation and can use a variety of objective functions that do not need to be differentiable; this flexible permits using accuracy as a target metric for classification tasks and could pose a significant benefit for temporally coded SNNs. Additionally, a property of especial interest is the fact since evolutionary methods directly explore the parameter space, they are not constrained by requiring spiking activity in order to propagate gradients and update parameters the same way the surrogate gradient methods require.

3.4.2 Prior Work on Spiking Neuroevolution

An early work on the neuroevolution of SNNs from 2005 was (81), where a parallelized implementation of the differential evolution algorithm was used to map sub-populations of networks to separate processors. For this work, extremely small SNNs based on a Spike Response Model dynamics were evolved to solve the XOR problem as well as the Iris flower classification task. A more recent work utilizing the SpiNNaker neuromorphic hardware system utilized the NEAT algorithm to evolve SNNs that solve the XOR problem as well as play the Pac-Man arcade game. Similar to the

work from 2005, SNNs in the population were mapped to a 48-chip system for efficient evaluation with the results being fed back into the NEAT algorithm(99). A hybrid approach utilizing ANN-SNN conversion followed by differential evolution of the neuron thresholds was carried out on the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 datasets. It is worth noting that as a population based evolutionary algorithm, differential evolution cannot as easily explore the entire parameter space when compared to evolutionary strategies and it also does not account for interdependence between the parameters, making crossover less effective(64) . Another recent approach for the evolution of SNNs was to utilize Hyper Neuroevolution of Augmenting Topologies (HyperNEAT). In this work the NEAT algorithm was used to evolve a compositional pattern producing network (CPPN) which then outputs the weights and synaptic delays for a SNN. This work compares results on both classification and control tasks with EONS, another evolutionary framework for SNNs which features a population-based genetic algorithm approach with crossover and mutation operators. In EONS, the encoding of the genome details information such as firing thresholds, leakage parameters, weights, or any other number of associated parameters, making it a flexible framework that can be tailored for different target neuromorphic architectures (23; 90) . Further evolutionary research also investigated the inclusion of Spike Timing Dependent Plasticity (STDP) to optimize the weights of the network while the architecture was evolved as well as exploring the evolution of SNN ensembles (21; 22) . In SPENSER, a bi-level approach of a genetic algorithm and structured grammatical evolution is utilized to perform neural architecture search for CSNNs while the training of candidate networks is performed through surrogate gradient descent using the SNN-Torch framework. Their conclusions mention sluggish experiment execution times, with the high run-time likely being attributable to the evolutionary neural architecture search being implemented in high-level Python without JIT compilation and each member of the population being evaluated sequentially; these issues could be ameliorated by compiling the training loop for each architecture and running them on a multi-node cluster(11).

In summary, the vast majority of previous neuroevolution research on SNNs focus on either evolving the topology as a form of neural architecture search, or used the NEAT algorithm to coevolve the network structures and weights for small scale architectures. As such, there currently exists a notable gap in the investigation of modern evolution strategies when applied to larger scale SNNs in the hundreds of thousands of parameters; this can be primarily attributed to the lack of GPU-accelerated frameworks for SNNs and neuroevolutionary algorithms until recent years.

3.4.3 Evolutionary Strategy Algorithms

The two evolutionary algorithms utilized in this work are described below.

Low-Memory Matrix Adaptation ES (LM-MA-ES)

LM-MA-ES is an optimized version of the popular Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES)(36), both of which optimize a probabilistic model through iteratively generating, evaluating, and discarding sample solutions. They differ from classic genetic algorithms by modeling the implicit probability distribution of solutions rather than operating locally on samples of an explicit distribution. That is, rather than sampling a random distribution and then using recombination, mutation, and selection operators to improve solutions, the statistics describing the solution population are evolved. By not maintaining an explicit population, the CMA-ES family can more effectively traverse the search space for a given sample/population size, helping with generalization to higher

dimensions. However, the issue with the original CMA-ES is that it maintains a full covariance matrix describing the interlinkage of all the evolvable parameters, which with a $O(n^2)$ memory complexity can be prohibitively costly for large numbers of parameters common to neuroevolution.

Work on the Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (MA-ES) algorithm found that CMA-ES could be approximated with little performance loss while removing the covariance matrix update and removing the need to perform matrix square root operations on the covariance matrix through using a transformation matrix(7); the trick is that \sqrt{C} can be estimated directly by the model, saving computation. The Limited-Memory Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy algorithm used in this work further reduces the time and space complexity of MA-ES by requiring the transformation matrix be diagonal and low-rank, allowing M to be scaled to the thousands of parameters(63).

Cost-Reduction Fast-Moving Natural ES (CR-FM-NES)

CR-FM-NES is another optimized algorithm derived from a set of methods referred to as Natural Evolution Strategies. In NES algorithms, the objective is to maximize the expected value for the fitness of solutions sampled from a distribution rather than simply trying to maximize the individual fitness; this poses a significant advantage to genetic algorithms for example because information gleaned from poor performing solutions can also be leveraged to guide the search. Building off of ideas introduced by REINFORCE(104), the works of Policy Gradients with Parameter-based Exploration(91) and Natural Evolution Strategies (103) applied this population improvement approach to control tasks and black-box optimization. NES algorithms possess a number of connections to CMA-ES and its variants but differs in that it approximates the Fisher Information Matrix to compute the KL-Divergence of samples in the population; the motivation for this is to take steps which alter the network's output distribution at a constant rate rather than being slowed down by the loss/fitness landscape curvature (101; 103). In evolutionary strategies algorithms such as NES, it is also common to apply a rank-based fitness transformation to help mitigate early outliers from dominating the search and trapping the algorithm in a local optima(34). However, since NES approaches also similarly update a mean vector and covariance matrix, several algorithms have sought to incorporate optimizations to enable scaling to high-dimensional problems. CR-FM-NES is one such method, which is able to achieve linear time and space complexity through the use of a limited covariance matrix representation, similar to approaches such as LM-MA-ES.(74)

3.4.4 Scaling Neuroevolution: Indirect Encoding and Gradient-Assisted Algorithms

Indirect Encoding

For larger scale SNNs, however, neuroevolution may still prove a challenge once the parameter counts enter the millions or tens of millions and beyond. The issue of scaling for neuroevolution has been known for decades, with a prominent technique to combat the problem being the use of indirect encoding. Similar to how the phenotypic traits of an individual are not directly encoded in their genome but rather the product of complex interactions within a gene regulatory network, indirect encoding mechanisms are composed of a smaller dimensional genome and a decoding function which then maps it to the dimensions of the problem space. A prominent example of indirect encoding is HyperNEAT (95) , where a compositional pattern producing network is evolved using NEAT to generate the weights and topology of a larger target network; in this case the genome describes a CPPN, which then acts as the decoding function to generate the larger network's weights. Another work in

this vein is the Compressed Weight Search method (55) , where the genome describes coefficients which are then mapped to neural network weights using an inverse discrete cosine transform. Finally, hypernetworks follow this same line of research, with a smaller neural network being trained to produce the weights of a larger network potentially based on the current inputs; this data-dependent mechanism shares characteristics with attention mechanisms and enables a form of weight sharing where generalized motifs of network parameters are repeated across layers. (35)

Gradient Assisted Evolutionary Strategies

Some work has investigated the incorporation of surrogate gradients into ES algorithms in order to improve their performance. One such example is GuidedES(65), which claims to be advantageous over algorithms such as CMA-ES by not working with a full covariance matrix, however it does materialize an $n \times n$ matrix as part of its gradient subspace calculations where n is the number of parameters, making this approach infeasible for high-dimensional problems where it would be of interest. A more recent work on the subject of using surrogate gradient information in an ES approach does not suffer from this same issue; instead of biasing the population sampling to align with the surrogate gradient, the work by Meier et. al. performs finite difference evaluation along the surrogate gradient direction and orthogonalizes the remaining vectors(67). In doing so, the algorithm can estimate components of the true gradient which do not align with the biased surrogate gradient. In effect, these orthogonal vectors provide exploration capacity to the algorithm while the surrogate gradient provides exploitation, with each iteration working to align more closely with the true gradient. By doing so, previous gradient free estimates can be used as the surrogate gradient, allowing for gradual accumulation of information about the true gradient over successive steps similar to the functioning of a momentum based optimizer. Luckily in the case of SNNs there already exists an easy and extremely useful surrogate gradient that can be calculated by using a continuous relaxation of the activation functions when backpropagating through time; utilizing such information to drive gradient-assisted evolutionary strategies to optimize SNNs could prove especially valuable and is worthy of future investigation.

Chapter 4

Introducing Spyx: A JAX-Based SNN Framework

4.1 The Existing SNN Library Landscape

While a number of Python libraries already exist, the majority of them are built on or provide interfaces to the TensorFlow or PyTorch frameworks and occupy different niches in terms of target applications with some being research oriented while others are commercially targeted.

4.1.1 Research Libraries

The GeNN and mGeNN frameworks allow for the implementation of both bio-realistic and machine learning oriented SNNs on GPU hardware through the use of kernels tailored to their training. GeNN is a C++ library that also provides a Python interface as well as a GUI environment in the form of SpineML and SpineCreator and has been used for computational neuroscience research in simulating the olfactory system of insects for example(53). The recent features provided by mGeNN include the ability to convert architectures composed of dense, 2D convolution, and 2D average pooling layers defined in Tensorflow and Keras into spiking networks that can be run on the underlying GeNN simulator for NVIDIA graphics cards(54). The training methods offered within the mGeNN library include ANN2SNN conversion on either a rate or timing basis as well as the direct training of SNNs using e-prop(4) or EventProp(105).

Besides mGeNN, there are several frameworks for SNN training that exist within the PyTorch ecosystem. SNN_Torch (26), SpyTorch(109), and BindsNET(40) are PyTorch based frameworks built around autograd tools to enable training SNNs through surrogate gradients; a feature unique to SNN_Torch is that models can be deployed to either GPU or Graphcore's IPU system for accelerated training and inference. Norse (83) offers more bio-inspired neuron models such as Izhikevich and adaptive exponential models with the ability to train them in PyTorch with either surrogate gradients, adjoint gradient methods, or plasticity based learning rules such as STDP. Finally, SpikingJelly (27) offers an additional framework for training SNNs using PyTorch or CuPy as a backend to accelerate learning and contains tooling for converting ANNs to SNNs.

4.1.2 Commercial and Hardware-Targeted Libraries

SynSense's Rockpool (70) is a framework compatible with multiple deep learning backends such as PyTorch and JAX and is tailored for training SNNs capable of deployment on the company's neuromorphic chips. As a toolkit targeted for model deployment, it contains extra features for constraining SNN parameters such that they are able to be mapped onto hardware and frames parameters in terms of continuous time. Given its tailoring for hardware employment, Rockpool is not geared toward detailed bio-realistic neural simulations such as those capable of being performed by GeNN but rather for embedded signal processing(70).

Nengo and its deep learning component Nengo-DL (85) is a simulator for SNNs by Advanced Brain Research (ABR) that integrates the Neural Engineering Framework with Tensorflow and Keras, allowing for hybrid deep learning and spiking architectures that can also be deployed to a variety of hardware such as Intel's Loihi chip or onto FPGAs. Nengo includes the ability to optimize SNNs with both online learning rules as well as using a differentiable continuous relaxation of a LIF neuron during training; it is important to note that this latter method is not a surrogate gradient approach but rather a conversion based method as the model being trained does not have spiking dynamics in the forward pass. A notable difference between Nengo and other frameworks is its emphasis on use for research on cognitive modeling and as such treats SNNs as groups of arbitrarily connected populations rather than the layer-based structures common in deep learning.

Finally, Intel's own LavaDL is the library for developing event-based models for execution on the Loihi neuromorphic chip. The methods for training SNNs within lava-dl consist of SLAYER (93), DECOLLE (50), and ANN2SNN conversion, with trained models being exported to an hdf5 file for deployment as a Lava process on the Loihi architecture.

4.2 Fully Just-In-Time Compiled SNNs with Spyx

4.2.1 Overview

A significant issue with SNNs is that their extremely temporal nature makes them time-consuming to train directly. The motivation for Spyx is to provide a compact and modular framework that enables the entire training loop to be compiled and carried out on machine learning accelerators, negating the performance penalties associated with Python being an interpreted programming language. Spyx is built in a relatively new framework used by Google Brain and DeepMind named JAX which offers a simple interface for carrying out high-performance array computing. Adopting a functional programming paradigm, JAX contains auto-differentiation and function vectorization transformations and allows users to just-in-time (JIT) compile Python functions into machine learning intermediate representation instructions (MLIR) for execution on either GPUs or TPUs. This enables flexible implementation of programs for machine learning and other scientific applications that can then be scaled to large computing clusters and executed at the speed of compiled programs written in lower level languages such as C/C++ (2). The wider JAX ecosystem offers a rich set of both neural network and optimization libraries, with Flax (42) and Haiku (43) offering frameworks for neural network construction while Evosax and Optax provide access to state-of-the-art evolution strategies and gradient descent optimizers respectively(2; 57). By building on JAX and only implementing components unique to SNNs such as neuron models, surrogate gradient functions, activity regularization tools, and specialized data loading, Spyx is able to benefit from and leverage external advances such

```

1 import jax
2 import spyx
3 import spyx.nn as snn
4 import haiku as hk
5
6 # First, define a surrogate gradient function:
7 synapse = spyx.axn.Axon(spyx.axn.arctan())
8
9 def shd_snn(x):
10     # We can use Haiku's RNN tooling to stack layers and
11     # not worry about carrying the recurrent state
12     # through the training loop.
13     core = hk.DeepRNN([
14         hk.Linear(64, with_bias=False),
15         snn.LIF((64,), activation=synapse),
16         hk.Linear(64, with_bias=False),
17         snn.LIF((64,), activation=synapse),
18         hk.Linear(20, with_bias=False),
19         snn.LI((20,))
20     ])
21
22     # dynamic_unroll takes care of the recurrent state for the SNN
23     spikes, final_voltage = hk.dynamic_unroll(core, x,
24                                               core.initial_state(batch_size),
25                                               time_major=False, unroll=32)
26
27     return spikes, final_voltage
28
29 # Apply Haiku's transform to generate the pure
30 # function equivalent of our SNN.
31 SNN = hk.without_apply_rng(hk.transform(shd_snn))
32 params = SNN.init(rng=jax.random.PRNGKey(0), x=sample_batch)

```

Listing 1: Construction of a simple SNN in Spyx

as new deep learning hardware, gradient optimizers, or neuroevolution algorithms without requiring the library to be updated. At present Spyx only contains built-in tools for training rate-based SNNs however support for temporally coded SNNs will be implemented in an update in the near future.

4.2.2 Constructing an SNN

Specifically, Spyx leverages utilities within DeepMind's Haiku library to allow for simple and rapid prototyping of SNNs. Defining a suite of neuron models, surrogate activation, activity regularization, and loss functions, and data loading and augmentation utilities, Spyx allows the user to define an SNN by combining linear or convolutional layers as part of a recurrent neural network and then use Haiku's unroll transformation.

As seen in listing 1, SNNs can be constructed in Spyx by simply stacking layers, with the recurrent dynamics handled by Haiku and the internals of the neuron models. Additionally, Spyx neuron models can accept multi-axis input shapes allowing them to be directly stacked upon convolutional layers for example.

```

1  ##### In spyx.axn #####
2  def triangular(k=0.5):
3      def g(x):
4          return jnp.maximum(0, 1-jnp.abs(k*x))
5          return jax.jit(g)
6
7  #####
8  triangle = spyx.axn.triangular()
9  my_custom_surrogate = jax.jit(lambda x: 1 / (1+jnp.abs(x))**2)
10 custom_fwd = jax.jit(lambda x: jax.nn.hard_sigmoid(21*x))
11
12 surrogate1 = spyx.axn.Axon(triangle)
13 surrogate2 = spyx.axn.Axon(my_custom_surrogate)
14
15 snn_activation = spyx.axn.Axon(bwd=surrogate2, fwd=custom_fwd)

```

Listing 2: Spyx Surrogate Function

4.2.3 Defining Surrogate Gradients

Spyx offers a number of built in surrogate gradients which can be accessed by calling their associated higher order function. Listing 2 shows how Spyx takes the parameters for properties of the surrogate function and returns the compiled surrogate. Additionally, users can define their own by simply JIT compiling a lambda function and passing it to `spyx.axn.Axon()`.

4.2.4 Data Loading and Manipulation

In order to JIT compile the entire training loop, the entire dataset needs to be stored in the GPU's vRAM; while modern data-center grade GPUs offering up to 80GB of memory make this objective feasible, it would be preferable if the same levels of efficiency could be achieved on consumer hardware. Spyx achieves this through the trick of temporal compression on the neuromorphic data. The smallest available datatype in popular machine learning frameworks is an 8 bit unsigned integer, which when only storing a single spike is a waste of 7 bits. Trading away a small computation time penalty to save space, Spyx packs 8 spikes into each uint8 value when processing and loading the dataset and only unpacks the values to the full time scale on a batch-by-batch for processing by the SNN. This optimization means that the majority of the dataset is stored in 12.5% of the amount of memory it would otherwise require. The process of loading a dataset in Spyx and how to decompress a single batch is shown in listing 3. Additionally, Spyx offers a flexible shift augmentation tool that allows you to randomly shift the input events along a desired set of axes; note that it is more efficient to apply the shift augmentation before unpacking the spikes as doing so operates on a tensor that is eight times smaller. Finally, while Spyx does offer a growing set of built in data loaders, the user is free to use their own; all that is required to leverage the full efficiency of Spyx is to load the entire dataset as a `jax.numpy` array with the properly shaped axes so that it can be scanned and vectorized over.

```

1 # Make SHD Dataloader
2 shd_dl = spyx.data.SHD_loader(256,1024,700)
3
4 # Create augmentation function
5 # Shift along channel axis
6 aug = spyx.data.shift_augment(max_shift=16, axes=(-1,))
7
8 # Fetch entire shuffled training set and labels.
9 # The shuffle key should be changed each time you call
10 # *dataset*_dl.train_epoch
11 x, y = shd_dl.train_epoch(shuffle_key=jax.random.PRNGKey(0))
12
13 # x.shape = (25, 256, 128, 700) --> note 128 instead of 1024
14
15 # Extract a single batch from the training set
16 packed_events = x[0]
17 # Apply augmentation, in practice you would generate a new key each time
18 shift_packed_events = aug(packed_events, jax.random.PRNGKey(0))
19 # Decompress it
20 unpacked_events = jax.numpy.unpackbits(shift_packed_events, axis=1)
21
22 # Now we can pass it to the SNN's apply function to get a readout
23 readout_traces, final_voltage = SNN.apply(params, unpacked_events)

```

Listing 3: Decompressing neuromorphic data in Spyx

Figure 4.1: Compressed Versus Decompressed Neuromorphic Data with Spyx

4.2.5 Adding Regularization

Spyx offers two activity regularization methods for SNNs: silence and sparsity regularization. Silence regularization imposes a lower bound penalty on a layer's activity, where neurons firing below an average rate for the batch incur quadratic cost; this attempts to avoid the dead neuron problem by discouraging the optimization process from driving neurons into complete silence from which they cannot recover using surrogate gradients. The sparsity regularization function offered by Spyx imposes a layer-wise upper bound for spiking to discourage high firing rates and is adapted from sparse autoencoder training regimens.

Listing 4 showcases the various aspects of adding regularization to an SNN in Spyx. The first step is to add an Activity Regularization layer following the hidden activation layer of interest which allows for spikes to be accumulated. The next nuance is that Haiku's `transform_with_state` must be used in order to also return the initial regularization variable which is now required when applying the SNN to data. Finally, both lower and upper activity regularization functions can then be created and incorporated into the SNN evaluation function to augment the loss.

4.2.6 Summary

As it can be seen from this chapter, Spyx offers an exciting new capability to the neuromorphic research community by providing a modular and efficient SNN framework within the JAX ecosystem. For additional examples and tutorials on how to build training loops to optimize SNNs using Spyx, see the associated GitHub repository.

```

1 ##### Define An SNN with a regularization module #####
2 def simple_snn(x):
3
4     # apply the first SNN weight layer to the whole batch
5     # since it's temporally independent
6     x = hk.BatchApply(hk.Linear(64, with_bias=False))(x)
7
8     core = hk.DeepRNN([
9         snn.LIF((64,), activation=spyx.axn.Axon(spyx.axn.Triangular())),
10        spyx.axn.ActivityRegularization(), # Added to record hidden spikes
11        hk.Linear(20, with_bias=False),
12        snn.LI((20,))
13    ])
14
15    # static unroll for maximum performance
16    spikes, V = hk.dynamic_unroll(core, x,
17                                  core.initial_state(x.shape[0]),
18                                  time_major=False, unroll=32)
19    return spikes, V
20
21 ##### Intialize an SNN with state to save spike counts #####
22 #             *** note we use transform_with_state here! ***
23 SNN = hk.without_apply_rng(hk.transform_with_state(simple_snn))
24 params, reg_init = SNN.init(rng=jax.random.PRNGKey(0), x=sample_batch)
25 # reg_init is a set of all-zero vectors that we pass to SNN.apply
26
27 ##### Define Regularization functions #####
28 upper_reg = spyx.fn.sparsity_reg(16) # note that these are counts
29 lower_reg = spyx.fn.silence_reg(4) # as of the beta release of Spyx.
30
31 ##### Use spike counts to compute regularization penalty #####
32 def net_eval(weights, events, targets):
33     # SNN.apply now returns an additional value containing the
34     # spikes per neuron for each sample in the batch
35     readout, spike_counts = SNN.apply(weights, reg_init, events)
36     traces, V_f = readout
37     # pass the spike counts to the regularization functions and add to loss
38     # lambda is the regularization coefficient.
39     return spyx.fn.integral_crossentropy(traces, targets) + \
40           lambda * (upper_reg(spike_counts) + lower_reg(spike_counts))

```

Listing 4: Regularization Primitives

Chapter 5

Experimental Methodology and Results

5.1 NMNIST

5.1.1 Overview

Neuromorphic-MNIST (NMNIST)(78) is a variant of the original MNIST dataset, where each hand-written digit was displayed on a screen and scanned by a dynamic vision sensor (DVS) camera in a saccadic fashion to generate delta-encoded spike data. For ease of experimentation only the first of the three saccades is used to keep the number of time steps manageable. Although NMNIST presents higher dimensional inputs than SHD(15), its smaller number of classes offers an easier learning task than the SHD dataset presented later in this chapter.

5.1.2 Implementation

Both optimization methods were evaluated using the same SNN architecture: a single 512-LIF neuron hidden layer with a 10 neuron Leaky-Integrate (LI) output layer was used since recurrent convolutions are substantially more demanding and the objective for this study is to compare the relative performance of neuroevolution and surrogate gradients rather than achieve state of the art performance. Five trials with different set random seeds were conducted to provide a better estimate of each method's performance. Given NMNIST's input shape of $(2, 34, 34)$, these networks consisted of almost 1.2 million parameters, posing a worthy challenge to neuroevolutionary methods and requiring that they be memory efficient.

Surrogate Gradient Details

For surrogate gradients, both Straight Through Estimation (6) and an arctangent surrogate(26) were evaluated, with training occurring over 25 epochs using the Lion optimizer with weight decay of 0.001 and a learning rate of $2e-4$. These parameters were selected based on the earlier evaluation experiments conducted with the validation split. The loss function for this experiment as well as all other surrogate gradient experiments was minimization of the softmax crossentropy between the output layer's membrane potential and the target label which was converted to a one-hot vector.

Neuroevolution Details

Two neuroevolution algorithms were evaluated: Low-Memory Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (LM-MA-ES) and Cost-Reduction Fast-Moving Natural Evolution Strategy (CR-FM-NES). The motivation behind this is explained in depth in Chapter 3, where algorithms which have sub-quadratic memory complexity are a necessity in order to scale to reasonable SNN architecture sizes. Similar to tuning the learning rate in surrogate gradient methods, the initial value for sigma which controls the search step size has a significant impact on the outcome of the evolutionary search. For both algorithms the evosax(57) library implementation was used with a population size of 256 and an initial sigma of 0.03 which was found through an initial parameter sweep; evolution was carried out for 50 epochs over the dataset with a batch size of 256. The objective function employed was accuracy based on maximum membrane potential of the output layer.

5.1.3 Results

Table 5.1 displays the average accuracy and execution times of both surrogate gradient and the examined evolutionary approaches. The evolutionary approaches evaluated perform fairly well given a model size of over 1 million. Interestingly, they performed on par with using STE while using a better surrogate such as arctangent yielded an immediate gain of 5% in accuracy.

Algorithm	Val. Accuracy	Test Accuracy	Time (s)
Straight Through Estimation	91.01%	91.35%	9.64
Arctangent Surrogate Grad.	96.00%	96.04%	10.96
CR-FM-NES	89.22%	89.44%	415.78
LM-MA-ES	88.86%	89.28%	655.89

Table 5.1: Average MNIST Performance

5.2 Spoken Heidelberg Digits (SHD)

5.2.1 Overview

The Spoken Heidelberg Digit (SHD) dataset is another neuromorphic dataset for supervised learning. Consisting of audio recordings of speakers saying the digits zero through nine in both English and German, the data was converted into a 700 channel spike-based encoding using the LAUSCHER software tool which emulates the functionality of a cochlear implant. The dataset consists of approximately 10,000 samples across 12 speakers two of whom are only present in the test set, with competitive test set performances achieving over 80% accuracy on the test set(15). For this work, a randomly drawn 20% of the training split was held out for use as validation when determining optimal parameters and model architectures.

The Lion optimizer(13) was selected for this work based on initial testing that found it quite robust for training SNNs whereas the Adam(52) optimizer from the Optax(2) library was not successful in achieving stable optimization for the dataset at the time of writing. The first experiment conducted was to identify a suitable learning rate range for training models; this was carried out by training an SNN with a scheduled learning rate that gradually increased from a minuscule value to one which would be far too large. The resulting loss curve in figure 5.1 shows that around $2e-4$ the learning

rate becomes too large and training diverges. Based on this, the remainder of experiments in this work were carried out with learning rates between $5e-5$ and $2e-4$ predominately.

Figure 5.1: Learning Rate Warmup Curve

5.2.2 A Comparison of Neuron Models

Next, a comparison of the various neuron models and structures implemented in Spyx was conducted with the results depicted in figure 5.2. As it can be seen, the Recurrent LIF (RLIF) model outperforms the others when trained with an arctangent surrogate gradient, while the Integrate-And-Fire (IF) neuron performs markedly worse due to its lower temporal capacity. This experiment was carried out using the Lion optimizer for 500 epochs on the SHD dataset. The ALIF model is based on the adaptive neuron from research on LSNNs(3) and was also found to work quite well amenable to surrogate gradient or evolutionary optimization.

5.2.3 A Comparison of Surrogate Gradient Functions

Another experiment was carried out to evaluate different surrogate functions. As it can be seen in figure 5.3 SNN optimization is fairly robust to the choice of surrogate gradient function, with the only exception being the Straight Through Estimator which assumes the derivative of the spiking activation function is always equal to 1. The key insight from training SNNs with varying surrogates is that the learning rate must be tuned to each function, and that this experiment was conducted for just LIF neurons; other neuron models/architectures such as Recurrent-LIF will have different optimal ranges for both the learning rate and traits of the surrogate itself that determine the steepness of the slope.

Figure 5.2: Validation accuracy for varying spiking neuron models. Note that the non-leaky IF model performs the worst while the Recurrent and Adaptive LIF models add slight performance boosts.

Figure 5.3: A Comparison of Surrogate Gradient Functions

5.2.4 A Small-Scale Comparison of Neuroevolution and Surrogate Gradients

To compare the effectiveness of neuroevolutionary methods with surrogate gradients, small SNNs with 2 hidden layers of 64 Adaptive-LIF(3) neurons were optimized on the SHD dataset with a batch size of 256 and 128 channels and time steps for each sample. Table 5.2 shows the average validation and test accuracy as well as the optimization time for each method. Excitingly, in this smaller dimensional regime the CR-FM-NES method outperformed optimization with an arctangent surro-

Algorithm	Validation Accuracy	Test Accuracy	Time (s)
Surrogate Gradients	76.84%	68.69%	101.38
CR-FM-NES	76.22%	73.26%	1755.33

Table 5.2: SHD: Neuroevolution vs. Surrogate Gradients

gate gradient with better generalization to the test set albeit at over an order of magnitude longer execution time. SHD’s larger number of target labels made it more difficult for evolution to improve when using accuracy as the objective function, requiring 2,500 epochs to achieve competitive performance; this downside was improved upon through the use of a spike-rate mean-squared error loss function that gave the evolutionary optimizer more guidance on how to suppress errant spikes in the output layer. To accommodate spike rate mean-squared error, the final layer for the evolution optimized networks was composed of LIF neurons instead of the standard LI neurons used for surrogate gradient architectures.

5.2.5 Evaluating the Scalability of Spyx on SHD

The results of experiments to test the efficiency of Spyx for training SNNs of varying input and hidden layer sizes as well as for differing time horizons are shown in tables 5.3-5.6. The experiments were conducted on an NVIDIA A6000 GPU accompanied by 8 CPU cores; the times listed are for the completion of 500 epochs that consist of both training and validation evaluations and include the time required to perform JIT compilation which takes approximately 10 seconds for the given configuration of SNN unrolling. Excitingly, it can be seen from the data that Spyx scales nearly linearly with the number of time steps, with a slight slowdown for 1024 time steps. It is also important to note that these execution times are connected to the batch size, with larger batches resulting in lower overall execution times so long as the entire batch can run on the GPU simultaneously. A key highlight is that in table 5.6, an SNN with 700 input channels and two hidden layers of 512 LIF neurons for a total of 632,832 parameters was able to be simulated for 1024 time steps and trained for over 500 epochs in under 13 minutes; this demonstrates that BPTT can be performed on sizeable SNN models at millisecond timescales in a practical and efficient manner. Assuming the trend would follow for 1536 time steps which is on par with millisecond level training on SHD, 500 epochs would take approximately 20 minutes and 3,000 epochs approximately 2 hours if the pattern holds; this would compare favorably to the 16 hours reported to conduct 10-fold cross-validation on SHD at 300 epochs per fold using GeNN(75). However, given the experimental results in this work lower temporal precision should suffice for normal applications. Besides the time demands of BPTT, another usual concern is the $\mathcal{O}(nT)$ memory complexity that scales as the product of the number of neurons and time steps(26); for 10GB of vRAM this translates to a computational budget where SNNs of up to a few million parameters should be able to be simulated for 1,000 time steps.

Channels	128 Steps	256 Steps	512 Steps	1024 Steps
72	46.7	82.5	154.6	292.4
128	47.3	83.0	153.5	298.0
256	47.9	85.0	157.8	303.5
384	49.1	86.7	161.8	310.3
512	49.1	86.8	163.7	373.8
640	51.1	89.4	167.2	412.6
700	51.2	90.4	169.2	395.2

Table 5.3: 64 Neuron Hidden Layer Size

Channels	128 Steps	256 Steps	512 Steps	1024 Steps
72	50.5	91.6	175.9	332.8
128	51.3	92.0	175.0	338.5
256	52.3	93.2	177.7	347.2
384	53.0	95.3	180.7	347.9
512	53.7	97.0	182.3	384.0
640	54.6	99.2	186.3	414.4
700	54.8	99.3	188.2	392.9

Table 5.4: 128 Neuron Hidden Layer Size

Channels	128 Steps	256 Steps	512 Steps	1024 Steps
72	63.4	116.6	223.7	438.1
128	63.9	116.3	225.6	441.0
256	64.5	120.6	226.4	443.8
384	65.4	123.9	232.4	451.4
512	66.0	124.7	236.6	468.9
640	67.4	127.5	242.5	492.7
700	67.3	125.6	238.7	485.0

Table 5.5: 256 Neuron Hidden Layer Size

Channels	128 Steps	256 Steps	512 Steps	1024 Steps
72	94.5	178.6	349.6	694.1
128	95.1	179.6	354.1	694.8
256	95.5	183.8	354.8	698.0
384	97.7	191.2	362.9	714.4
512	98.4	192.5	365.7	735.7
640	100.1	196.8	372.2	780.8
700	100.8	192.7	374.1	771.0

Table 5.6: 512 Neuron Hidden Layer Size

Figure 5.4: Examining Learning Rate and Gradient Centralization

5.2.6 Training an RSNN

Finally, using the lessons learned from the scaling experiments and neuron model comparisons an attempt to train a competitive RSNN was done. For this, a batch size of 256 samples was used with 256 input channels and 128 time steps for the dataset while the Lion optimizer was employed with a learning rate of $1e-4$ for 1500 epochs. Crucially, gradient centralization(108) was utilized in order to stabilize the loss over time as an alternative to batch normalization, eliminating the spikes in error seen in the blue curve of figure 5.4. Combined, these conditions allowed for a RSNN which achieves 94% validation accuracy and 85% test accuracy. The important result of this experiment is that Spyx can train high performing SNNs the same as other existing libraries but at extremely rapid rates.

Chapter 6

Future Work and Conclusions

6.1 Future Directions

While this thesis provides key first steps towards further research into the efficient and rapid investigation of spiking neural network optimization, there are myriad avenues for immediate exploration. First of all, this work only compared the performance of neuroevolution with surrogate gradient methods for training rate-based SNNs; future work needs to investigate the viability of neuroevolution for optimizing temporally-coded SNNs which are known to be more difficult for surrogate gradient techniques. As part of this investigation, Spyx will need to be expanded to facilitate the training of phasor networks(12; 77) and their conversion to spiking equivalents to provide a comprehensive evaluation. Other conversion and distillation methods as well as local learning techniques are also potential additions for augmenting the capabilities of Spyx for allowing comparison of different SNN learning algorithms in the same framework. More experiments to determine properties of loss functions, regularization, and augmentation as well as research into the efficient neuroevolution of convolutional architectures and performing neural architecture search are also areas of interest.

Secondly, the examination of gradient-assisted neuroevolution and memetic algorithms to leverage the utility of surrogate gradient information while mitigating its bias and dependence on spikes to trigger weight updates could provide great benefit to the optimization process. In such a scheme, evolutionary optimization approaches that incorporate surrogate gradients could work to obtain a more useful gradient direction for optimizing parameters, or in a memetic construction surrogate gradient methods could act as a local search operator to refine candidates produced by an evolutionary strategy algorithm. The combination of surrogate gradient and evolutionary approaches would also overcome the issue of dead neurons by allowing weight updates to happen regardless of spiking and also combat issues with vanishing or exploding gradients.

Third, the introduction of Spyx promises to accelerate research into SNNs for control tasks through the multitude of JAX-based reinforcement learning environments. Through the use of evosax(57) and environments such as gymmax(58) and Jumanji(10), SNNs could be optimized using neuroevolution to solve tasks such as cartpole or vehicle routing. An even more exciting direction is the exploration of Quality-Diversity algorithms for optimizing SNNs to perform locomotion tasks using the QDax(62) and Brax(30) libraries; such work would enable the evolution of diverse neuromorphic controllers for robots in a time and computationally efficient manner.

Finally, several enhancements for the Spyx library are also planned in order to support the training of larger SNN architectures. These improvements include stochastic neuron models inspired

by SPSN(106) and the implementation of Spiking-RWKV(116) layers in order to facilitate high-performance training of spiking language models and spiking state space machine architectures; these deep learning inspired SNN architectures both feature the ability to be trained via convolution and as such require additional functionality by Spyx to incorporate. Improving Spyx to support such training will also require considerations for multi-GPU/TPU training and improved scalability. Additionally, Spyx will feature an interface for exporting SNN models to Neuromorphic Intermediate Representation (NIR) (82) to enable transferring models trained on GPUs or TPUs onto energy efficient neuromorphic hardware for inference; the scaling and performance of Spyx on Google's TPU architecture is also a planned subject of future research. Additionally, since neuroevolution is highly parallelizable but not as demanding on memory, the potential to leverage older generation GPUs with smaller per device memory in large clusters for SNN training also offers promise.

6.2 Summary of Results

Thanks to the extreme efficiency afforded by just-in-time compilation of the SNN learning/evolution process, this work was able to carry out several studies on the effects of various techniques on the direct training of SNNs. Achieving impressive scalability on a single GPU, Spyx allows for the training or evolution of SNNs with hundreds of thousands of parameters in mere minutes on a single GPU, with the time complexity scaling on a near linear basis. Experiments on the Neuromorphic-MNIST dataset found that neuroevolution can successfully scale to SNNs with over a million parameters and achieve competitive performance with surrogate gradients. Furthermore, for smaller network architectures on the SHD dataset neuroevolution was found to yield networks that generalize better than those trained with surrogate gradient descent. However, given the substantial increase in computational requirements for evolutionary methods, the best route forward lies in the hybridization of surrogate and evolutionary based methods to achieve the best of both worlds. This work serves as a first step in further experimentation into neuroevolutionary methods which will be required to better understand their capabilities with respect to SNN optimization.

Finally, the release of Spyx as another tool for experimenting with SNNs will hopefully accelerate research on both basic SNN properties as well as the hybridization of SNNs with other deep learning architectures such as state space machines to achieve both high metric performance and greater energy efficiency. As it can be seen, Spyx drastically lowers the entry barrier for a host of exciting new research directions by allowing SNNs to be trained at incredible speed, allowing faster prototyping and iteration of ideas. In conclusion, Spyx offers a notable contribution to the field of neuromorphic computing through dramatically shortening the time and hardware required to perform fundamental SNN research.

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